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**New data on *Cleomenes putaoensis* Lazarev & Murzin, 2020 and
Dere tatarianae Lazarev & Murzin, 2020 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract: The closest species to *Cleomenes putaoensis* Lazarev & Murzin, 2020 is *C. assamensis* Gardner, 1926. The distinguishing characters are described. The closest species to *Dere tatarianae* Lazarev & Murzin, 2020 is *D. cassiae* Gardner, 1939. The distinguishing characters are described.

Introduction

The new information on the closest taxa (with holotypes photos) to recently described new species was now received from Tomáš Tichý.

Results

***Cleomenes assamensis* Gardner, 1926**

Fig. 2

Cleomenes assamensis Gardner, 1926: 208 - Assam, Naga Hills.

Differential diagnosis. *C. assamensis* differs from *C. putaoensis* (Fig. 1) by elongated 2nd antennal joint (pedicellum), which is transverse in *C. putaoensis*; 4th antennal joint in *C. assamensis* longer than 5th in 1.1 times, but in *C. putaoensis* - 1.2 times; 1st antennal joint (scapus) in *C. assamensis* thicker; femora distinctly less clavate; elytral punctation much smaller; apical elytral spines shorter; body length 13 mm just as in the holotype of *C. putaoensis*.

The distance between type localities is about 320 km.

Type material. Photo by T. Tichý of the holotype from Inde, Assam, Naga Hills, 7.4.1924, collected by S. N. Chatterjee and preserved in the Natural History Museum, London (not in Forest Research

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Institute, Dehra Dun as it was stated in the original description).

***Dere cassiae* Gardner, 1939**

Fig. 4

Dere cassiae Gardner, 1939: 12 - Shwebo, Burma; 1942: 70 (key) - Burma.

Differential diagnosis. *D. cassiae* differs from *D. tatiana*e (Fig. 3) by more convex pronotum with very distinct deep punctation, while in *D. tatiana*e pronotum relatively flat with diffused punctation disappearing in the middle near posterior margin; scutellum in *D. cassiae* triangular, while in *D. tatiana*e rounded; elytra in *D. cassiae* greenish-blue, while in *D. tatiana*e - dark-blue; elytral punctation in *D. cassiae* more distinct; elytral apex in *D. tatiana*e deeply emarginated; body size 8.5-10 mm; body length of *D. tatiana*e is 8.5 mm.

The distance between type localities is about 430 km.

Type material. Photo by T. Tichý of the holotype from Burma, Shwebo preserved in the Natural History Museum, London.

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Fig. 1. *Cleomenes putaensis* Lazarev & Murzin, 2020: holotype, female, Myanmar (N Burma), 50 km E Putao, environs Nan Thi vill., 950 m, 11-16.5.1998, S. Murzin & V. Sinyaev leg.

Fig. 2. *Cleomenes assamensis* Gardner, 1926: holotype from Inde, Assam, Naga Hills, 7.4.1924 (photo by T. Tichý).

Fig. 3. *Dere tatianae* Lazarev & Murzin, 2020: holotype, female, NW Thailand, Mae Hong Son, Suen Pu, 5.5.1992, Strnad Jen leg.

Fig. 4. *Dere cassiae* Gardner, 1939: holotype from Burma, Shwebo (photo by T. Tichý).

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